

Simulation based study of Inverted-T FINFETs under Nanoscale Dimension

Iqbal Preet Singh (Student I.D. 40058514)

Abstract

In this project a novel structure known as “Inverted-T FINFETs” has been studied. High performance characteristics of this structure are observed along with looking at some of the drawbacks arising from the geometrical configuration and causing short channel effects. Simulation has been carried out for various devices with different geometrical parameter (for important feature size) to understand the root cause of the problem. It has been observed that by performing device simulations using Comsol multiphysics, an optimally designed structure can be designed to overcome some of the drawbacks while retaining the benefits of IT FINFETs, specially having a large current in on-condition, which is achieved because IT FINFETs have advantage of both vertical fin and ultra-thin horizontal body as per it’s device structure. A comparison has been with the current technology node of devices such as conventional FINFETs, under same dimensions, IT FINFETs provide larger drain-current. An optimally designed IT FINFETs are showing good prospect for the future, especially for application requiring high on-state current.

Introduction

Scaling of semiconductor devices has been ongoing at a significant pace over the last three decades as predicted by Moore’s law [1], which is number transistor on the chip will double every year. At the same time, there are some adverse effects with scaling of traditional MOSFETs such as severe short channel effects [2] and reduction of on-state current. These effect leads to performance degradation. Many device structures have been implemented to overcome these short channel effects, one of the most popular device studied and realized is a FINFET [3], reason being the three-dimensional structure which provides more gate control by extending the gate to the three sides of the fin. However, the on-state current is not significantly high in these FINFET structures.

Further, there are some disadvantages of FINFET [4] such as the space between the fins is not utilized, low on-state current, and due to the high ratio of height of fin to width of fin, there can be some difficulties in etching during the fabrication process. One of the relatively new device structure [5-7] called “inverted-T FINFET” can overcome some of these weakness of the FINFET structure. Especially these IT FINFET can have large on-state current as these devices have larger channel width, compared to FINFET, by having an ultra-thin body between the fins.

Along with the significant improvement in the on-state current by IT FINFETs, there are some drawbacks of this novel structure such as the formation of the ungated area in the body of the fin which can lead to severe short channel effect such as DIBL, these problems can be negated to some extent by closing monitoring the geometric and physical parameters of IT FINFETs.

Therefore, by varying the geometric parameters of the structure carefully, an optimal IT FINFET can be realized.

In this project, IT FINFETs will be studied by performing device simulations in Comsol multiphysics [8]. A comparison with FINFET has also been done to validate the improvement of on-state current. Geometric and physical parameters of IT FINFET are studied to have satisfactory view for the future applicability of these devices. Device structure and simulation approach has been discussed in the Section II. Section III delivers the simulation results and handful discussion on understanding the results as per device physics perspective. Conclusion is discussed in Section IV.

Device structure and simulation approach

The IT FINFET device structure, is consisting of the fin and ultra-thin body at the area between the fins. For the study, the height of the fin has been taken as constant which is set to be 25 nm (which is in agreement with the international roadmap of semiconductor [9]). The height of ultra-thin body can also impact the device performance which has also been investigated, simultaneously the width of the fin can also impact the device behavior. The benefit of IT FINFET structure is having the same dimension (for important feature size such as gate length) compared to FINFET, but still having an extended channel due to the ultra-thin body. The simulation study is carried out for the single fin as a representative to understand the device behavior, simultaneously reducing the computation complexity. Figure 1(a) shows the schematic of the IT FINFET in which we can see that the word 'T' is used due to the configuration of the fin.

For the simulations, Comsol multiphysics has been used. A single p-type fin is under investigation. The substrate thickness has been considered equal to 100 nm (referred to the current commercial technology node). Hafnium oxide of thickness 3 nm is used as a gate insulator. The work function for the gate insulator [10] is considered to be 4.6 eV. Material parameters for silicon are taken from the pre-defined library of comsol multiphysics. The channel and source/drain (S/D) doping concentrations [6] are 10^{15} cm^{-3} for n-type and $5 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for p-type respectively. Meshing has been done appropriately in such a way that any change in mesh size does not affect the results, however a fine mesh is taken into consideration. Figure 2(b) reports the simulated geometry of IT FINFET designed in comsol multiphysics.

Results and Discussion

The geometry shown in Figure 1(b) is studied in comsol multiphysics, along with studying the one with the inactive area between the fins such as FINFET to see the impact of the ultra-thin body, to investigate the benefit of IT FINFETs over conventional FINFETs. One such benefit is high on-state current and which is quite understandable due to presence of larger width of channel in IT FINFETs due to presence of ultra-thin body, at the same time having same dimension of important feature size in both the structure. One such observation is studied in

Figure 2 where the comparison of on-state current has been made for IT FINFET and FINFET under same dimensions (height and width of the fin, and gate length). We can observe that on-state current is increased by one order of magnitude and can be explained by extra carrier concentration in the ultra-thin body.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic description of IT FINFET (taken from [6]) (b) Simulated geometry in COMSOL Multiphysics

Figure 2. Simulation results from COMSOL Multiphysics for P-type FINFET and Inverted-T FINFET (height of ultra-thin body is 3nm)

Owing to benefits of the structure, there are also some concerning drawbacks. One such problem is that gate is not covering the whole three faces of the fin due to the presence of the ultra-thin body which can form the ungated region which is not controlled by the gate and has

weaker fringing field. The bigger the width of the fin, the larger will be the ungated region. This ungated region, due to presence of minimized gate control is more prone to short channel effects (SCE), one such SCE is Drain induced barrier lowering. Punchthrough is also observed as the width is relatively increased. Figure 3 (a) shows the schematic cross section of the fin to illustrate the ungated region and Figure 3 (b) shows the variation of DIBL as a function of fin width, which shows that as fin width increases, the short channel effect gets worse.

Energy band diagram at completely off state can also provide more insight to the effects of this ungated region. Figure 4 shows the energy band diagram for different fin width. There is no saturation seen for dV/dx when the gate width is increased more than 10 nm. The most important device structure optimisation that can be done in IT FINFETs is the reduction of the ungated region. One probable solution is reducing the width of the fin to 10 nm or less.

Figure 3. (a) Cross sectional view of the fin depicting the ungated region due to the presence of ultra-thin body (taken from [6]). (b) I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio and DIBL as function of Fin width (taken from [6]).

Figure 4. Energy band diagram for P-type Inverted-T FINFET under off-state condition (Drain voltage = -0.7 V, Gate voltage= 0.6 V). This graph is taken from [6].

Figure 5. Simulation results from comsol multiphysics for P-type Inverted-T FINFET with different width of FIN (height of ultra-thin body is 3nm)

Now with realization that to reduce the impact of SCE due to the ungated region, width of the fin should not be more than 10 nm, it would be worth looking at the on-state current of IT FINFET with different width of the fin, to understand the impact of the fin width on the state current. The benefit of the novel structure of IT FINFETs is the relatively large on-state current. If that characteristic is maintained along with satisfying the reduction of SCE, an optimal design can be obtained, having better device performance along with reduced tradeoff effects. Figure 5 shows the simulated on-state current for IT FINFETs with different width of the FIN. It can be seen that there is reduction of on-state current which is quite expected but the reduction is not significant, the on-state current is still higher than the conventional FINFET. This can be due to charge carrier density in the ultra-thin body. This is a very important result, as we can obtain the benefit of large on-state current present in IT FINFET along with negotiation of negative effects that comes with specific device structure.

Further, to understand the potential drop along the width of the channel can provide an insight for the characteristics of the device and variation of the potential. To a different context, this change in potential can also be used to observe the channel breakdown. But in this project this has been seen to verify the potential drop and look into the channel characteristics. Figure 6 shows the potential along the width of the channel (it is taken for width equal to 40 nm) and ultra-thin body with equal to 30 nm. However we have seen that optimal fin width should be less than 10 nm, still the behaviour of this potential drop will be same, exponential across the

edges of the fin. In Figure 6, kinks are observed which are due to the presence of mesh size equal to 10 nm, a much smaller mesh size would give a smooth curve, however due to non-presence of such computational capacity, this observation cannot be made. A much smoother curve is seen for the similar figure simulated in [6].

Figure 6. Simulated potential along the body (drain voltage = -0.7 V, Gate voltage = -1.4 V). Presence of kinks due to mesh points (taken as 10 nm). A much finer mesh (1 nm) can make it smoother.

Additionally, the height of ultra-thin body can impact the device performance in a significant way. One such observation which is quite understandable is as the height of fin increases, the carrier density increases, and the on-state current would also increase. At the same time, subthreshold swing would suffer understandably as the carrier concentration increases, the gate control decreases, subthreshold swing decreases. It has been reported and simulated in [6], a height of ultra-thin body less than 2 nm would not give any high-performance characteristics that are obtained from IT FINFETs. In this project we have taken height of the ultra-thin body equal to 3 nm which is providing high on-state current with subthreshold swing of 64 mV/decade. Such tradeoff are made for the optimal design of IT FINFET to achieve the high device performance due to the structural design. Figure 7(a) depicts the transfer curve characteristics with different height of the ultra-thin body, whereas 7(b) shows the subthreshold swing with varying height of the ultra-thin body. One more important feature size, which is the gate length. Figure 8 shows the transfer characteristics with varying gate length, no significant change is observed in transfer characteristics with varying gate length, however 10 nm gate length is observed to show subthreshold swing close to 60 mV/decade. Thus, looking at the width of fin, height of ultra-thin body and gate length, we can make sure for optimal design for IT FINFETs.

Figure 7. (a) Transfer characteristics with varying height of ultra-thin body for a p-type IT FinFET (taken from [6]). (b) Subthreshold swing with varying height of ultra-thin body (taken from [6]).

Figure 8. Transfer characteristics with varying gate length for P-type IT FinFET (taken from [6]). A comparison has also been made with 5 nm and 20 nm FinFET.

Conclusion

With its novel structure, IT FINFETs provides significant advantage over the planar mosfet and the three dimensional structure such as FINFETs. Simultaneously, we have discussed about some of the drawbacks presented by this novel structure mainly because of the device geometry. Simulation showed that IT FINFETs with fin width of 10 nm or less can overcome the short channel effects arising from the ungated region and still provide large drain-current as compared to conventional FINFET. Also the critical thickness for the height of the ultra-thin body is seen to be 3 nm, below which drain current is substantially reduced, above 3 nm it can impact the subthreshold swing impacting the device performance. Despite the fact that IT FINFETs are more prone to short channel effect (SCE) due to inherent geometric configuration, it is shown in this project that a correctly designed IT FINFET is much superior to conventional FINFET in terms of large drain current, at the same time having reasonable SCEs.

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